

Tsallis and Kaniadakis Formalism and the Breaking of $p(e_1)p(e_2)=p(e_1+e_2)$

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Newtonian mechanics with action-reaction dictates conservation of momentum and one may use conservation of kinetic energy in certain cases. For an ideal gas, Maxwell-Boltzmann or Shannon treatments depend on elastic collisions and assume that $p(e_1)p(e_2) = p(e_1+e_2)$ ((1)), which minimizes the information required about a system. In other words, the form of $p(e_i) = C \exp(-e_i/T)$ essentially carries the same information e_i/T for all e_i/T , whether they are large or small. This comes at the price of infinite terms in: $\exp(-x) = \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} (-x)^n / n!$

Although this assumption holds in many cases, there is no a priori reason to believe that a collision between $e-\delta$ and $e+\delta$ is the same as one between $2e-\delta$ and δ . In other words, there does not seem to be any a priori reason for assuming ((1)), we argue. There could be many reasons for ((1)) not to hold in the physical world. The Fermi-Dirac and Bose-Einstein cases are two examples, but there could be cases for which there is single particle energy discrimination.

We suggest that Tsallis and Kaniadakis formalisms are two examples. One may see that in the case of $e_i/T \ll 1$ (in both cases), one has a probability which mimics $\exp(-e_i/T)$ to first or second order in e_i/T . To the first and second orders concerned, ((1)) holds.

Even if such an $e_i/T \ll 1$ collides with another $e_i/T \ll 1$, however, one starts to see a deviation in the product from the RHS of ((1)) to higher orders in the Kaniadakis case. We argue that this means that the system handles $e_i + e_j$ in a manner linked to their values and not the sum as in the Maxwell-Boltzmann case and examine some properties of these situations. In particular, both the Tsallis and Kaniadakis cases yield falling power laws for $e_i/T \gg 1$ which clearly breaks ((1)) and so one sees a transition from $e_i/T \ll 1$ which is Maxwell-Boltzmann like with ((1)) because the variable $(-e_i/T)$ is multiplied by either $1-q$ or k and $q=1$ or $k=0$ is like $e_i/T \ll 1$.

We note that in (1), nonlinear kinematics is derived to deal with the Kaniadakis and other cases, but we argue that one may argue a priori that ((1)) need not hold in all cases.

Maxwell-Boltzmann Case

The MB case may be derived from action-reaction time balance for elastic two body scattering:

$$e_1+e_2 = e_3+e_4 \text{ ((2a)) and } p(e_1)p(e_2) = p(e_3)p(e_4) \text{ ((2b))}$$

Taking \ln of ((2b)) and equating to a constant $(-1/T)$ times ((2a)) yields:

$$\ln(p(e_i)) = -e_i/T \rightarrow p(e_i) \text{ unnormalized} = \exp(-e_i/T) \text{ and } p(e_i) \text{ normalized} = C \exp(-e_i/T) \text{ ((3))}$$

The interaction cannot discern the different e_i values or e_i/T in terms of the mathematical form of $p(e)$. This leads to an infinite number of terms in $\exp(-x) = \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} x^n / n!$. Physically, this need not be the case.

If one questions a distribution $\exp(-e_i/T)$ with an infinite number of terms, one may argue for one with a finite number, say power one in e_i/T or a quadratic term for $e_i/T \ll 1$. There are consequences on ((2b)), however, for such a finite power series.

Why Should the e_i/T Case Yield the First or Second Order Expansion of $\exp(-e_i/T)$ in the Tsallis and Kaniadakis Cases?

The Tsallis and Kaniadakis cases are a priori said to be power law distributions which become the Maxwell-Boltzmann distribution when a power parameter, $1/(1-q)$ (Tsallis) and $1/k$ (Kaniadakis) become infinite, i.e. $q=1$ and $k=0$. This, we argue, introduces assumptions in that one has a single power parameter and secondly one wishes to retrieve the MB distribution for $k=0$ or $q=1$.

Given these assumptions, it seems that one cannot escape the result that for $e_i/T \ll 1$, the base function (which is taken to a power) must become $1 - e_i/T$ to lowest order in e_i/T . In particular, the MB case is realized not only for $q=1$ or $k=0$, but also for $e_i/T \ll 1$ because this variable is multiplied by either $(1-q)$ or k in the Tsallis and Kaniadakis cases.

In the Tsallis case utilizes only order one has, but in the Kaniadakis case one has two orders. In the e_i/T limit and both of these orders must match an expansion of $\exp(-e_i/T)$, otherwise one does not have: $\exp q(-e_i/T)$ (Tsallis) and $\exp k(-e_i/T)$ (Kaniadakis) transitioning to $\exp(-e_i/T)$. Thus, the base functions in the Tsallis and Kaniadakis cases don't discriminate much between e_i/T for e_i/T small in terms of mat form, but do as e_i/T becomes larger. In fact, the requirement that the distribution become a falling power law in e_i/T completely destroys ((1)).

Some Properties of the Tsallis and Kaniadakis Distributions

The Tsallis and Kaniadakis distributions are represented by a base function to a fixed power $1/(1-q)$ or $1/k$. If $0 < k < 1$, the $k=1/2$ or $k=1/3$ means $1/k = 2$ or 3 , i.e. an integer power. The fact that the base function must represent an expansion of $\exp(-e_i/T)$ for e_i/T has strong consequences. For example, if one consider the Kaniadakis case with $k=1/n$, then $1/k = n$ and one has:

$$p(e) \text{ unnormalized} = \{ 1/n (-e_i/T) + \text{sqrt}[1 + 1/(nn) (e_i e_i / TT)] \} \text{ power } n \quad ((4))$$

It is already known that for $k=0$ or $e_i/T \ll 1$, this must match $\exp(-e_i/T)$. If, one, however, uses $e_i/T \ll 1$ without creating an exponential, then ((4)) becomes:

$$\begin{aligned} p(e) \text{ unnormalized} &= \{ 1 + (-e_i/T) + 1/n (e_i e_i / TT) .5 + (n \text{ choose } 2) (e_i e_i / TT) (1/nn) \} \\ &= 1 + (-e_i/T) + .5 (e_i e_i / TT) \quad ((5)) \text{ which is the expansion of } \exp(-e_i/T) \end{aligned}$$

to second order in $(-e_i/T)$. One may see, however, that this feature is broken for $e_i/T \ll 1$ and $e_j/T \ll 1$ unless one only keeps first order in e/T for the Tsallis case and up to second order for the Kaniadakis, i.e.

$$p(e_i)p(e_j) \text{ not} = p(e_i+e_j) \quad ((6))$$

Thus, as q is no longer 1, or $k > 0$ or e_i/T not tiny, one moves away from the approximately held $p(e_i)p(e_j) = p(e_i+e_j)$, meaning that the system can distinguish between e_i values in terms of math functional form. This is to be expected because as $e_i/T \gg 1$, one expects a power law drop-off and one may see that ((6)) is definitely the case then.

In particular, for the Tsallis case:

$$\exp_q(-e_i/T) = \{1 - (1-q) e_i/T\}^{\text{power } 1/(1-q)} \quad ((7))$$

If $e_i/T \gg 1$, then one may drop the leading 1 and obtain: $\{(1-q) e_i/T\}^{\text{power } 1/(1-q)}$

This should be a function dropping with e_i , so $q > 1$. The transition to a power law shows one cannot have $p(e_1)p(e_2) = p(e_1+e_2)$, except in an approximation for $e_i/T \ll 1$. The transition towards a power law shows that different e_i/T values are treated very differently by the probability function.

In the Kaniadakis case:

$$\{-ke_i/T + \sqrt{1 + kke_i/T}\}^{\text{power } 1/k} \approx \{.5/(ke_i/T)\}^{\text{power } 1/k} \quad ((8))$$

$0 < k < 1$ so this is already a dropping power law. Again, a transition from an almost $\exp(-e_i/T)$ with $p(e_1)p(e_2) = p(e_1+e_2)$ for $e_1/T \ll 1$, $e_2/T \ll 1$ to a power law shows how ((6)) comes into play.

The transition to a dropping power law for high e_i/T already distinguishes these high e_i values' behaviour from a low e_i/T one showing that even though energy is conserved $e_1+e_2=e_3+e_4$, probabilities contain more information about e_i/T than simply its value as in the Maxwell-Boltzmann case.

Argument for Non-Linear Kinematics

We note that (1) provides detailed collision calculations arguing that one does not always have $p(e_1)p(e_2) = p(e_1+e_2)$ as in the Boltzmann transport equation.

Conclusion

In conclusion, we note that $p(e_1)p(e_2) = p(e_1+e_2)$, which holds in the Maxwell-Boltzmann case, is linked with $p(e_i)$ unnormalized = $\exp(-e_i/T)$. In other words, the same math functional form holds for all e_i/T and has the property $\exp(-e_1/T)\exp(-e_2/T) = \exp(-(e_1+e_2)/T)$. Thus, the probability only reveals the value of $-e_i/T$ and an infinite number of terms in $\exp(-x) = \sum \text{over } i (-x)^i / i!$ are needed.

The Tsallis and Kaniadakis distributions assume a power law falloff for $e_i/T \gg 1$, but not for $e_i/T \ll 1$, which means that the probability function $p(e_i)$ already distinguishes between high e_i/T

and low and so cannot satisfy the MB $p(e_1)p(e_2)=p(e_1+e_2)$. This condition holds in approximation for $e_i/T \ll 1$ because both of these distributions utilize the variable $(1-q)^{-e_i/T}$ or $k^{-e_i/T}$ in the base function which is taken to the power of $1/(1-q)$ or $1/k$. Thus, the limit $q=1$, or $k=0$ is the same as $e_i/T \ll 1$ and yields a MB like solution. As $e_i/T \gg 1$, one must transition to a falling power law which clearly violates $p(e_1)p(e_2) = p(e_1+e_2)$, showing how a single parameter used in a base function to power allows one to transition from low e_i/T results which satisfy the MB condition ((1)), to falling power laws which do not. Physically, it seems that there is no reason for a collision to treat all e_i values the same such that e_i+e_j follows the same process as e_1+e_2 , even though they both sum to the same value.

References

1. Kaniadakis, G. NonLinear Kinetics Underlying Generalized Statistics
<https://arxiv.org/pdf/cond-mat/0103467>